

Social Media Engagement and Social Appearance Anxiety in Teenagers: An Analysis of Correlational Links and Gender Differences

Punita B. Deori and Rajlakhimi Bharati

Department of Psychology, University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya

This research aimed at examining the relation between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among. A sample total of 150 participants (n=150; where 75=female & 75=male) from selected Higher Secondary Schools of Sipajhar, Darrang District, Assam, were taken. Furthermore, the survey assessed “social media engagement” and “social appearance anxiety” by using the Social Media Engagement Scale for Adolescents (SMES-A) (Ni et al., 2020) and Social Appearance Anxiety Scale (SAAS) (Hart et al., 2008). Data analysis was done by using descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation and percentage and inferential statistics such as independent sample t-test and Pearson's correlation by using advance Excel and SPSS. Findings revealed a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.70$) between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among teenagers. The results indicated no significant gender-based differences in social media interaction and social appearance related anxiety among teenagers.

Keywords: Social media, social media engagement, social appearance, social anxiety and teenagers

Today's digital landscape is heavily influenced by the social media platforms including Snapchat, Instagram, Facebook and Twitter, which strongly influence teenagers nowadays and how teenagers perceive themselves and interact with others in a social context. These platforms function as visual spaces where adolescents compare themselves and their appearance to the idealized beauty standards shaped by filters, edits and curated content. Because of that, many teenagers feel the burden to meet those unrealistic standards, leading to increased focus on likes, comments and validation from others. These constant comparisons and need for others' approval contribute to social appearance anxiety, where the individual becomes overly concerned about how others might judge them or think of them by their looks and these exposures can lower self-esteem, increase fear of negative evaluation and might create dissatisfaction with one's appearance (Thompson et al., 1999). Although social media offers a wide range of opportunities for self-expression and connection, it also promotes comparison, insecurity and emotional distress, which ultimately heightens teenagers' social appearance anxiety.

Social Media Engagement

Social media engagement refers to how individuals connect with content across a wide variety of platforms through liking, sharing, reacting, commenting, posting updates, stories and videos (Kaplan

& Haenlein, 2010). It reflects the degree of engagement, involvement and emotional commitment a person invests in online communication. Singh (2024) reported excessive social media use among adolescents and found that adolescents with higher levels of social media engagement are more prone to behavioural problems like emotional distress, conduct issues, hyperactivity and peer-related problems showing a positive correlation between social media engagement and other behavioural and mental health concerns. Mallick et al. (2024) reported a strong statistically significant relation between social media engagement and poorer mental health outcomes in Assam, which might result in intensifying emotional distress, self-comparison and digital dependency. Ghosh (2021) highlighted the growing dependency of smart-phones and social media among students as they are the vulnerable population due to academic stress, emotional exhaustion, work-load and long working hours. Anand (2025) highlighted the relation between social media engagement, appearance-based anxiety and body image concern among college-going students and found that although social media usage plays a vital role in shaping the perception of perfect beauty, its impact varies across individuals depending on factors like resilience, self-esteem, confidence and values. Joshy et al. (2025) indicate a strong link between social media involvement and social anxiety and behaviour associated with body image avoidance, which also highlights that individuals who are anxious about social interactions are more likely to avoid situations where their physical appearance might be judged. Singh et al. (2024) revealed that excessive mobile dependency or social media involvement, also termed as nomophobia, is significantly associated with mental health concerns, psychological distress and appearance-related concerns. Hedge et al. (2023) found that approximately 68.49% of students exhibited selfitis, among them 51.12% are classified as borderline and 16.13% as acute, and 1.24% as chronic. The study highlighted that frequent selfie-taking behaviour as a form of social media engagement is associated with appearance anxiety, self-comparison and also associated with

Author Note

Dr. Punita B. Deori, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya
Rajlakhimi Bharati, Student, Undergraduate, Department of Psychology, University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya
We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.
Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Dr. Punita B. Deori, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology University of Science and Technology, Meghalaya
E-mail: punitadeori@gmail.com

constant validation seeking. Piko et al. (2023) revealed that 9.8% of adolescents are at high risk of disordered eating due to factors such as excessive weekly internet use, which results in elevated BMI scores. Smith (2025) found that subjective engagement like emotional involvement with social media platforms rather than time spent is a stronger predictor of appearance anxiety. Tian et al. (2025) found that social media engagement leads to upward social comparison, which significantly increases appearance-related concerns.

Social Appearance Anxiety

Social Appearance Anxiety represents a psychological state where individuals experience persistent distress and self-consciousness regarding how their physical features are perceived by others (Hart et al., 2008). Social appearance anxiety is often associated with dissatisfaction regarding physical appearance, body image, persistent concern about appearance and often tries to avoid social situations where one's looks or physical features might be evaluated (Clark & Wells, 1995). It is very evident in today's modern era, specifically in teenagers, as it is a crucial developmental stage marked by peer influence, identity crisis, strong sensitivity to social acceptance and increased awareness of body image (Steinberg, 2014). Kumari et al. (2025) found that considerable number of post-graduate students who experienced low self-esteem and moderate to high levels of loneliness are significantly associated with higher social appearance anxiety. The study explained that individuals with low self-esteem were prone to experience a high level of concern about how others will perceive their looks and it turns out, pushing the individual the verge of loneliness and isolation. According to Riya (2024), there is a significant link between the apprehension regarding negative assessment from others and the development of social appearance anxiety. It suggests that a high level of fear of being negatively judged by how they look is more prone to social anxiety and appearance-based anxiety and also no significant gender-based differentiation was found. Behera and Khuntia (2025) found that self-objectification increases appearance anxiety, while resilience reduces it, suggesting that resilient persons with high self-esteem are better equipped to resist the societal beauty standards and the pressure to achieve those standards. Behera and Pandey (2024) found that social appearance anxiety negatively impacts psychological adjustment, self-esteem and resilience. Pramanik (2024) revealed that low or poor peer relationships and self-perception of body image leads to higher body dissatisfaction and appearance anxiety during adolescents, which is a phase marked by heightened social comparison and sensitivity to peer comparison. Raghavan and Fathima (2024) reported that appearance anxiety significantly predicts social interaction anxiety, suggesting that concerns about one's appearance can cause discomfort and apprehension in social settings. Valsalan and Prasad (2024) concluded that higher appearance anxiety is linked with lower self-esteem among young adults. The study highlights the importance of early interventions that focus on improving confidence, promoting body positivity, and resilience against social media pressure. Kaushik and Batra (2022) found a significant correlation between body shame, appearance anxiety and reduced mental health and overall well-being, suggesting that body shaming strongly contributes to appearance anxiety and poor mental health. Research by Wang (2025) indicates that the link between social media dependency and the onset of depressive symptoms is largely explained by the mediating influence of appearance-related anxiety.

The study discussed various factors promoting social appearance anxiety, including the high frequency of social media usage and body image monitoring. Üstündağ et al. (2024) found that higher appearance anxiety, which increases with higher anxiety levels, is strongly linked to a 54.4% rise in appearance-related consciousness among adolescents when using social media. The author suggested that this form of appearance anxiety acts as a catalyst for negative self-perception, leading teenagers to view their own appearance through a more critical lens while online.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the relationship between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among teenagers.
- To compare the levels of social appearance anxiety between male and female teenagers.
- To compare the levels of social media engagement between male and female teenagers.

Hypotheses of the Study

- *H01*: There will be no significant correlation between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among teenagers.
- *H02*: There will be no significant difference in social appearance anxiety between male and female teenagers.
- *H03*: There will be no significant difference in social media engagement between male and female teenagers.

Method

Participants

In the present study, the sample consisted of 150 participants aged 15 to 19 years from Standard IX to XII of the selected high schools in Sipajhar, Darrang district, Assam. To avoid age-related variability and ensure developmental homogeneity among the participants, participants from these specific grade levels were selected. Out of the total sample, 75 participants were male and 75 participants were female, ensuring equal gender representation. The purposive sampling method was utilized, guaranteeing that solely students who actively used social media were considered.

Research Design

The present study was a correlational study in nature, which intends to investigate the relation between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among teenagers.

Measures

Social Appearance Anxiety Scale (SAAS), to measure social appearance anxiety, consisted of 16 items (Hart et al., 2008) was used. Participants rated each item on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (*not at all*) to 5 (*extremely*), resulting in a possible total score between 16 and 80. Within this scoring framework, higher cumulative values are indicative of more intense anxiety regarding one's physical appearance. The scale demonstrates excellent internal consistency ($\alpha = 0.90-0.94$) (Hart et al., 2008) and strong test-retest reliability (0.800-0.90) (Hart et al., 2008) and strong construct validity. *The Social Media Engagement Scale* for adolescents of Ni, Shao, Geng, Qu, Niu, and Wang (Ni et al., 2020) consisted of 15 items, with every item rated on a 5-point Likert scale. The scoring system, which ranged from 1 '*strongly disagree*' to 5 '*strongly agree*' was

constructed to assess the extent and nature of adolescent's; engagement with social media platforms. The scale demonstrates acceptable and good internal consistency (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.710.80$) (Ni et al., 2020) and strong construct validity which accurately measures affective, behavioral & cognitive engagement.

Procedure

The researcher physically went to the chosen schools and obtained formal approval from the school administrations of the chosen high secondary schools in Sipajhar, Darrang district to guarantee adherence and ethical standards. Prior consent was taken from the participants of the study, followed by the administration of the "Social Appearance Anxiety Scale" and "Social Media Engagement Scale" in designated classrooms. The researchers assured that the data collection occurred in a secure and calm setting, which would reduce any possible stress for the participants.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, specifically mean, standard deviation and percentage, to profile the participants' demographic characteristics and summarize the distribution of social media engagement and social appearance related anxiety scores were computed. Inferential statistics, such as Pearson's Correlation were computed to examine the relationship between two variables and an independent sample t-test to assess gender difference (Male & Female) in Social Appearance Anxiety and Social Media Engagement. For analysis, Advanced Excel and SPSS were used with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

Objective-wise results were discussed below-

Objective 1: To Examine the Relationship Between Social Media Engagement and Social Appearance Anxiety among Teenagers.

H01: There will be no significant correlation between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety among Teenagers

Table 1

Correlation between Social Media Engagement (SME) and Social Appearance Anxiety (SAA)

Variables	Correlation (r)	p
SME vs SAA	0.70	<.001

Note. Level of significance was set at 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). The obtained p-value ($p < .001$) indicates that the result is statistically significant.

Table 1 depicts a strong positive correlation (r) between Social Media Engagement and Social Appearance Anxiety among teenagers ($r = 0.70$). The p-value ($p < .001$) is less than the significant level of 0.05 suggesting that the relationship is statistically significant. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming a statistically significant link between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety. This finding suggests that as teenagers' involvement with social media platforms increases, their level of anxiety regarding appearance related judgement also rises significantly.

The finding is supported by the findings of Tesfaye and Harris (2025) who assessed the link between social media's association with social appearance anxiety and revealed that increased social media use is positively associated with higher levels of social

appearance anxiety among users. The findings of Wang (2025) found that excessive social media engagement contributes to heightened appearance-related concerns and psychological distress among students. Hegde et al. (2024) also revealed through their study that a positive correlation exists between selfie-taking behavior and appearance anxiety, indicating that higher engagement in appearance-focused online activities is associated with greater concern about physical appearance.

Objective 2: To compare the level of Social Appearance Anxiety between Male and Female Teenagers

H02: There will be no significant difference in social appearance anxiety between male and female participants.

Table 2

Independent Samples t-test for Gender Differences in Social Appearance Anxiety (SAA)

Variables	t	p
SAA	-1.62	.10

Note. Level of significance was set at 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). The obtained p-value ($p = .10$) is greater than 0.05, indicating that the result is not statistically significant.

Table 2 depicts the value of the independent sample t-test as -1.62 with a corresponding p-value of 0.10 and since the p-value is greater than the conventional level of significance ($p > 0.05$), the result is not statistically significant. Therefore, it suggests that there is no significant difference in social appearance anxiety level between male and female participants. Hence, the null hypothesis (H02) is accepted or fails to reject.

The findings of the present study are supported by the findings of Riya (2024) which reveal that there are no significant gender differences in social appearance anxiety among young adults. Raghavan and Fathima (2024) found no significant gender difference in appearance anxiety. Similarly, Soraisam and Saikia (2024) reported no gender difference in body shaming, showing that both males and females are equally affected by appearance-related pressures.

Objective 3: To compare the level of Social Media Engagement between Male and Female Teenagers

H03: There will be no significant difference in social media engagement between male and female participants.

Table 3

Independent Samples t-test for Gender Differences in Social Media Engagement (SME)

Variables	t	p
SMES	-0.41	.68

Note. Level of significance was set at 0.05 ($\alpha = 0.05$). The obtained p-value ($p = .68$) is greater than 0.05, indicating that the result is not statistically significant.

Table 3 indicates that the obtained t-value was -0.41, with a corresponding p-value of 0.68. Since the p-value is greater than the conventional level of significance ($p > 0.05$), the result is not statistically significant. Hence, there is no significant difference in social media engagement levels between male and female participants. Hence, the null hypothesis (H03) is accepted or fails to reject.

The present finding is supported by Smith and Caitlin (2025) who found no significant gender difference in social media usage, with engagement based more on personal preferences than gender. Similarly, Piko et al. (2023) reported that adolescent online activity is influenced by contextual and behavioral factors rather than gender alone. Singh (2024) also noted high social media use among school-going adolescents without major gender differences, suggesting that social media serves as a common platform for both males and females.

Conclusion

In the modern technological age, social media has become a significant part of teenagers' everyday routine. It shapes their sense of identity through interaction, self-presentation, and social validation, but also exposes them to continuous comparison, idealized appearances, and societal beauty expectations. The constant exposure to this environment can shape a teenager's perception of their physical appearance and increase sensitivity to how they are evaluated by others. It has the potential to raise concerns related to physical appearance, often referred to as social appearance anxiety, have emerged as a significant psychological issue among teenagers. The findings of the present study revealed a significant positive relationship between social media engagement and social appearance anxiety. It can be assumed that increased engagement with social media platforms is associated with higher levels of concern regarding physical appearance. This highlights the psychological impact of digital environments where consistent exposure to idealized images, peer comparison, and validation-seeking behaviors contribute to appearance-related anxiety among adolescents.

The current analysis also revealed that there is no meaningful disparity between genders regarding social media usage or appearance-related anxiety. These findings suggest that digital pressure and the resulting concerns over physical appearance are not gender-specific. Rather, they appear to be pervasive issues that transcend gender lines and have an impact on all teenagers equally in today's interconnected digital environment. In the present study, an important contribution lies in its focus on teenagers from a rural population in Sipajhar, Darrang district of Assam. The findings demonstrate that even in rural settings where traditional lifestyles and cultural values are more prominent, social media has become an integral part of teenagers' daily lives and significantly influences their psychological experiences. Despite comparatively different socio-cultural and environmental conditions from urban areas, teenagers in rural regions are equally exposed to digital platforms and the associated pressures of appearance and social evaluation.

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